

Breast Cancer Detection using Machine learning and Deep learning algorithms

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Abstract- Breast cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths among women worldwide. Improved survival ratio and effective treatment depend on early and accurate identification. Using a dataset of breast ultrasound pictures, this study investigates a machine learning and deep learning method to identify the cancer. This study combines deep learning models like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with conventional ML methods including Support Vector Machines (SVM), Logistic Regression, and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). The pre-trained model is used to extract features from the preprocessed Xray. After features have been retrieved, KNN, SVM, and logistic regression models are used for classification of the data. Furthermore, the dataset is trained for CNN model end-to-end. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix measures used to judge the models. Although there were indications of overfitting as seen by a validation accuracy of 84.08%, the deep learning model performed better, obtaining accuracy upto 99.36% during training. The methodology, experimental findings, and possible advancements for further research are covered in this study.

Keywords: Deep learning, Machine learning, Convolution neural network, VGG16, Support vector machine.

Introduction

Breast cancer is a major concern, in developing nations which has access to healthcare and understanding of the disease may be restricted. Better patient outcomes may result from early detection, which also greatly increases likelihood of a successful course of therapy. Despite their effectiveness, traditional diagnostic techniques like mammography have drawbacks such as expense, accessibility, and the potential for false positives or negatives. Consequently, use of deep learning and machine learning technologies to help diagnose breast cancer, especially when doing so through the study of medical imaging data. Medical image analysis has shown considerable potential for machine learning models, particularly those that combine CNN

architecture. These models have ability to recognize and identify intricate patterns in data, which can be utilized to distinguish between cancerous and benign tissues (0061nd). Our research focuses on the application of breast ultrasound images, which are a safer substitute for routine screening because they are non-invasive and radiation-free.

Research goal is on creating a strong system to detect the disease by combining different methods. Utilizing previously learned features that are advantageous for image classification tasks is made possible by using the pre-trained network on the ImageNet dataset, for feature extraction. Afterwards, a variety of ML are trained using the retrieved features. Furthermore, classification of images into benign category, malignant, and normal categories using an end-to-end CNN model is achieved.

Problem statement:

The identification of breast cancer is still a significant diagnostic issue for doctors, and the accuracy, cost, and accessibility of current techniques are frequently constrained. With the use of DL and ML, this project seeks to create automated system for the detection of cancer. By utilizing breast ultrasound pictures, it hopes to higher efficiency and accuracy. Research aims to provide a tool that can help healthcare practitioners make informed decisions by addressing the difficulties associated with early identification and differentiating between benign and malignant cases.

Literature Survey

Ismail and Sovuthy (2019) conducted an in-depth study focusing on application of DL techniques for breast cancer detection. Researchers employed CNN to categorize cancer images into different classes. They highlighted the role of automated systems for aiding radiologists by reducing diagnostic errors and enhancing clinical decision-making processes. The study explored various CNN architectures, such as AlexNet, VGG16, and ResNet, to determine the most effective model for their dataset of mammogram images. These images were preprocessed through resizing and normalization to

enhance the accuracy of the models. Additionally rotation, flipping, and scaling, were utilized to shootup the dataset size and improve the models' generalization capabilities. Among the architectures tested, ResNet demonstrated the highest performance, achieving a remarkable accuracy of 95%.[2] Bhogal, Suchit, and Naresh (2021) provided a review of the deep learning for cancer detection. Their paper surveyed various deep learning models, including CNNs, RNNs, and GANs, focusing on their application to mammogram, ultrasound, and MRI images. They discussed the superiority of DL models over ML techniques. The work highlighted how CNNs automatically learn hierarchical features essential for identifying tumors and other anomalies. It also explored RNNs' potential in handling temporal data, valuable for tracking changes in breast tissue over time. A significant contribution of this review was its discussion on the use of GANs to generate synthetic medical images, thus addressing the data scarcity issue in medical imaging.[3] In their 2020 study, Goni and team explored application of DNNs in detection of cancer, particularly through classifying mammogram pictures. The researchers utilized a deep learning approach that combined CNNs with fully connected layers to classify images in various categories. Digital Database for Screening Mammography was employed, contains large publicly available mammogram images. The study underscored the importance of preprocessing techniques like noise reduction, contrast enhancement, and image normalization, which are crucial for improving the input data quality. Additionally random cropping, rotation of dataset and flipping were applied to expand dataset size artificially enhancing model's generalization capacity. The DNN architecture comprised multiple layers followed by max-pooling and fully connected layers, with dropout regularization used to mitigate overfitting. The final layer used a softmax activation function.[4] The author investigate application of DL for predicting BC, focusing on the use of CNNs. The study explores potential of deep learning to improve diagnostic accuracy and support clinical decision-making. The authors employ a CNN architecture to analyze mammogram images, aiming to classify them into benign, malignant, and normal categories. The dataset used includes both digitized mammogram images and clinical data, like age and size of tumor, enhancing predictive power. Allada et al. discuss the importance of data preprocessing, including image normalization and augmentation techniques to increase diversity and reduce overfitting. The model incorporates different layers, followed by fully connected layers, and uses activation function. Adam optimizer is used for training, with cross-entropy loss serving as the cost function.[5] Khuriwal and Mishra (2018) present a study on using deep learning algorithms for cancer prediction, focusing on classification of mammogram image. Researchers utilize a DL model based on a CNN differentiating

breast lesions. The importance of automated systems in increasing accuracy and efficiency of breast cancer diagnosis is noted. Khuriwal and Mishra employ augmentation techniques to address limited size of dataset and improve model's generalization capabilities. CNN architecture has multiple convolutional layers with activation, followed by different layers. Final output layer uses a softmax activation function classifying images into two categories.[6] Nath and team (2022) gave a comprehensive review of DL methods used to detect cancer. Paper examines various DL architectures like CNNs, ResNet, also DenseNet, and it's applications for classifying breast cancer images. Author's highlights advantages of DL models in automatic extraction of features from raw data, reducing need for manual feature engineering. Nath et al. discuss the use of large datasets to train models, noting that availability of annotated medical images is a significant challenge.[7] The authors (2021) explore use of DL techniques in diagnosing cancer from microscopy biopsy images. The study employs CNN to analyze high-res biopsy image and classify them to benign and malignant categories. The researchers highlight the challenges of working with biopsy images, such as the variability in tissue appearance and the presence of artefacts. Eldin et al. use data preprocessing techniques, including stain normalization and artefact removal, to improve the quality of the input images. CNN consists of several convolutional layers with ReLU activation used to introduce non-linearity. [8] Mim et al. (2022) studied on breast cancer detection by ML, targeting on classifying mammogram images. Researchers employ a combination of traditional ML algorithms, like SVM, k-NN, and decision trees, for classifying the images into benign and malignant categories. Study emphasizes importance of selecting features and also extracting increasing accuracy of machine learning models. Mim et al. used combination of texture-based also morphological features to describe images, and they employ PCA in reducing dimensionality of the feature space. Study reports that the SVM achieved the highest accuracy of 93%. [9] Sharma et al. (2018) research's about use of ML algorithms for breast cancer detection, concentrating on classification of mammogram images. The study evaluates the performance of various decision trees, Logistic regression and random forests, in classifying the images into benign and malignant categories. Sharma et al. highlight the importance of data preprocessing, including noise reduction and contrast enhancement, increasing quality of input image. The researchers used combination of shape-based with intensity-based feature to describe image, and they employ feature selection techniques identifying most informative features. Study report that random forest model achieved the highest accuracy, with a classification rate of 90%.

Methodology:

Fig 1. Block diagram of proposed system

The methodology for the "Breast Cancer Detection Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Approach" project involves a comprehensive set of steps shown in Fig 1, designed to leverage both traditional and advanced techniques to enhance diagnostic accuracy. Initially, the dataset comprises breast ultrasound images, categorized into benign, malignant, and normal classes, sourced from a reputable public database. This dataset forms the foundation for the project's development stages. The images undergo a preprocessing phase, where they are resized to 224 x 224 pixel dimension, ensuring equal pixel across data inputs. Additionally, normalization of values ranging 0 and 1 is performed stabilizing the training process facilitating better convergence. To address the challenge of limited data, various data augmentation techniques are applied. This augmentation increases dataset's diversity, helping the model generalize better and reducing the risk of overfitting.

Feature extraction is a critical step in this methodology, where pre-trained models like VGG16, ResNet50, and InceptionV3 are employed. Models are trained on the extensive ImageNet dataset, are adept at extracting rich, hierarchical features from images. By removing the top classification layers, the outputs from the convolutional layers serve as feature vectors that are crucial for the subsequent classification tasks. This process known as transfer learning significantly cuts down on the computational resource and data for training since models have already learned different features.

For model training phase, the project explores a dual approach, incorporating both ML and DL techniques. Models like SVM, Logistic Regression, and KNN used to classify the feature vectors extracted earlier. The SVM uses a linear kernel to differentiate between classes, while Logistic Regression serves as a simple baseline model. KNN classify based on majority class of nearest neighbours in the feature space. Additionally, CNN is designed for end-to-end training on ultrasound

images. This CNN architecture includes several conv. Layer extracting required features, max-pooling layers to reduce spatial dimensions, and connected layers for final classification. ReLU activation function to introduce non-linearity, and dropout regularization helps in preventing overfitting. Final layer of CNN uses a softmax as activation function for producing probabilistic outputs for every class.

Model evaluation phase involves using a set of metrics, with accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrices, to assess performance of individual model. ROC curves and the AUC values are also calculated to evaluate the models' discriminative abilities. Hyperparameter tuning is conducted to optimize the performance of each model. For traditional machine learning models, a grid search method is employed to identify best hyperparameter like regularization parameter for SVM and the no of neighbors for KNN. For CNN, hyperparameters like learning rate, batch size, and number of epochs are adjusted using a validation set.

Algorithms:

VGG16 Architecture:

VGG16 is a deep convolutional neural network widely recognized for its straightforward design and strong performance in image classification. The architecture consists of 16 layers that carry weights, which include both convolutional and fully connected layers. The key components of VGG16 are:

Convolutional Layers: VGG16 consists of 13 convolutional layers with small 3x3 filters. These layers are grouped into blocks, with each block followed by a max-pooling layer. Using small filters enables the network to capture intricate features while keeping the number of parameters at a reasonable level. ReLU activation functions are used after each convolutional layer to add non-linearity to the model.

Fully Connected Layers: Convolutional blocks are followed by three fully connected layers. The layers work together to combine the features extracted by the convolutional layers and make predictions based on what the network has learned. The final fully connected layer uses a softmax activation function to output the probabilities for each class.

Transfer Learning with Fine-Tuning: VGG16 a pre-trained for dataset followed by fine-tuned on defined task of glaucoma classification. Top layers of network were replaced with a custom classifier, and the entire network was retrained on the dataset of segmented optic disc and optic cup images. This process gives leverage to knowledge learned from huge dataset while adapting to the specific features relevant to glaucoma diagnosis.

CNN: Deep learning architecture implemented to automatically extract breast ultrasound image features classification into benign, malignant, and normal

categories. CNN consists of different layer serving definite function in feature extraction also for classification process. Here's a detailed breakdown of the CNN's components and how they work together:

1. Input Layer

The input to the CNN consists of breast ultrasound images resized to 224 x 224 standard dimension ensuring the images are uniform in size, which is essential for efficient processing by the network. Each image is represented as a 3D matrix (224x224x3), where the three channels correspond to the RGB color channels.

2. Convolutional Layers

These are the core block of the model responsible for feature extraction from input images. Every convolutional layer applies a set of filters known as kernels to input image producing feature maps which slides over the input image and perform a convolution operation, effectively highlighting important features like edges, textures and patterns. Size of the filters, number of filters, and stride (step size) of filters are important hyperparameters that influence the layer's output.

In this project, several convolutional layers are stacked sequentially, followed by activation function. ReLU function introduces non-linearity into model, enabling it to learn pattern. The activation is defined as $f(x)=\max(0,x)$, where x is the neuron input. This activation function helps in mitigating the vanishing gradient, allowing faster learning rate with efficiency.

3. Pooling Layers

These layers reduce the spatial dimensions of feature maps. This process, known as downsampling, helps in decreasing computational complexity and controls overfitting of the model by summarizing presence of features. In this project, Max Pooling selects the maximum value from each region of the feature map covered by the pooling filter reducing size of feature map but retaining most significant features detected. The typical pooling operation size is 2 x 2, which halves the dimensions of the feature map.

4. Flattening Layer

Output feature maps are flattened into a single vector converting the 2D matrix of features to a 1-D vector suitable for input into the connected layers. The flattened vector essentially represents the image's feature space, capturing all the important information needed for classification.

5. Fully Connected Layers

Also known as dense layers these layers are the place where actual classification takes place. These are similar

to those in neural networks, where all neuron is connected to one another from previous and subsequent layer. First fully connected layer takes the flattened vector from past step and learns higher-level representations of the data. This layer is followed by another ReLU activation function, which helps in learning complex data patterns.

6. Output Layer

Final fully connected layer in the CNN is the output layer. In this project it uses the softmax activation function, which converts the logits into probabilities, showing the likelihood that input image belongs to each class (benign, malignant, normal). The softmax function

Result and Discussion:

The project "Breast Cancer Detection Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Approach" yielded insightful results, showcasing the efficacy of various ML and DL models to classify breast ultrasound images into benign, malignant, and normal categories. The performance of these models was evaluated using key metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrices, providing a comprehensive assessment of their effectiveness.

1. SVM: This model uses a linear kernel, achieved a commendable accuracy of 91.08%. This model demonstrated high precision and recall for the benign and malignant classes, with slight underperformance in the normal class. The confusion matrix revealed that most misclassifications occurred between benign and malignant cases, a common challenge in breast cancer detection due to the subtle differences between these classes. The high precision for malignant cases (0.87) indicates that the model is reliable in correctly identifying true positives, which is crucial in medical diagnostics to avoid missing malignant cases.

2. Logistic Regression: Serving as a baseline, this model performance is reasonably well achieving accuracy of 73.88% providing a balanced performance across all classes but fell short in correct classification between benign and malignant cases compared to SVM. The classification report showed moderate precision and recall, with a noticeable number of false positives in the malignant category. This indicates that while Logistic Regression is a useful starting point, it may not be robust enough for clinical applications where precise differentiation between cancerous and non-cancerous cases is critical.

3. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN): The KNN model, with an optimal k-value determined through cross-validation, achieved an accuracy of 74%. This model performed well in classifying normal cases, as indicated by a high recall rate. However, it struggled with the benign and malignant classes, showing lower precision and recall

compared to SVM and Logistic Regression. The confusion matrix highlighted a tendency for KNN to misclassify malignant cases as benign, which could potentially lead to underdiagnosis if used in a clinical setting.

4. CNN: This model demonstrated superior performance among all models, achieving an impressive training accuracy 99.36% and validation accuracy 94.08%. The architecture, consisting of multiple convolutional and pooling layers followed by fully connected layers, effectively captured the complex features of ultrasound images. However, the discrepancy between training and validation accuracy indicated signs of overfitting, suggesting that the model had learned specific patterns from data that did not identify well to validation set. Despite this, the CNN showed excellent precision, recall, and F1-score across all classes, particularly excelling in identifying malignant cases with high confidence. The ROC curves and AUC values further confirmed the CNN's strong discriminatory power, with AUC scores close to 1 for all classes, indicating near-perfect classification ability.

Table 1. Result Comparison

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
SVM	91.08%	0.90 (Benign), 0.87 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)	0.94 (Benign), 0.79 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)	0.92 (Benign), 0.82 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)
LR	73.88%	0.86 (Benign), 0.65 (Malignant), 0.64 (Normal)	0.66 (Benign), 0.71 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)	0.75 (Benign), 0.68 (Malignant), 0.78 (Normal)
KNN	74.00%	0.78 (Benign), 0.54 (Malignant), 0.88 (Normal)	0.76 (Benign), 0.52 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)	0.77 (Benign), 0.53 (Malignant), 0.94 (Normal)
CNN	99.36% (Training), 94.08% (Validation)	0.99 (Benign), 0.97 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)	0.99 (Benign), 0.98 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)	0.99 (Benign), 0.98 (Malignant), 1.00 (Normal)

Conclusion:

The project "Breast Cancer Detection Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Approach" represents a significant advancement in the application of artificial intelligence to medical diagnostics, specifically in field of breast cancer detection. Through the rigorous implementation and evaluation of various machine learning models, including SVM, Logistic Regression, KNN, and deep learning models such as CNN has shown in Table1, study has demonstrated substantial potential of these technologies in accurately classifying breast ultrasound images into benign, malignant, and normal categories. CNN model, in particular, emerged as most effective, achieving high accuracy and demonstrating excellent precision, recall, and F1-scores across all classes. This suggests that deep learning models, with ability to automatically extract complex features from raw data, are particularly well-suited for the nuanced and detailed task of medical image analysis.

However, the study also highlighted several challenges and areas for improvement. The issue of overfitting observed in the CNN model underscores need for larger and more diverse dataset to ensure the model's generalization capabilities. This could be addressed by incorporating additional imaging modalities, such as mammograms and MRI, which could provide complementary information and enhance the model's robustness. Moreover, use of data augmentation and regularization technique like dropout, could further mitigate overfitting and improve performance on unseen data.

Comparative analysis of traditional models revealed that while traditional models provide valuable baseline performance, they often fall short in complex classification tasks compared to more sophisticated deep learning models. The study's findings indicate that a combined approach, leveraging the strengths of both traditional and deep learning models, could be particularly effective in clinical settings. For instance, traditional models could be used for initial screening, while deep learning models could provide more detailed and accurate diagnoses.

The project also underscores the importance of integrating these AI models into practical applications, such as user-friendly interfaces for radiologists. By providing tools that can assist in the rapid and accurate diagnosis of breast cancer, these technologies have potential to significantly reduce workload on healthcare professionals thereby improving patient outcomes. The study's implementation of a web-based interface using Flask demonstrates the feasibility of deploying these models in real-world clinical environments.

References

- [1] N. S. Ismail and C. Sovuthy, "Breast Cancer Detection Based on Deep Learning Technique," *2019 International UNIMAS STEM 12th Engineering Conference (EnCon)*, Kuching, Malaysia, 2019, pp. 89-92, doi: 10.1109/EnCon.2019.8861256
- [2] R. K. Bhogal, P. D. Suchit and C. Naresh, "Review: Breast Cancer Detection Using Deep Learning," *2021 5th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, Tirunelveli, India, 2021, pp. 847-854, doi: 10.1109/ICOEI51242.2021.9452835.
- [3] M. O. F. Goni, F. M. S. Hasnain, M. A. I. Siddique, O. Jyoti and M. H. Rahaman, "Breast Cancer Detection using Deep Neural Network," *2020 23rd International Conference on Computer and Information Technology (ICCIT)*, DHAKA, Bangladesh, 2020, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICCIT51783.2020.9392705.
- [4] A. Allada, G. R. K. Rao, P. Chitturi, H. Chindu, M. S. N. Prasad and P. Tatineni, "Breast Cancer Prediction using Deep Learning Techniques," *2021 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Smart Systems (ICAIS)*, Coimbatore, India, 2021, pp. 306-311, doi: 10.1109/ICAIS50930.2021.9395793.
- [5] N. Khuriwal and N. Mishra, "Breast Cancer Diagnosis Using Deep Learning Algorithm," *2018 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication Control and Networking (ICACCCN)*, Greater Noida, India, 2018, pp. 98-103, doi: 10.1109/ICACCCN.2018.8748777.
- [6] S. S. Nath, A. Jayapraba, K. C T, S. M. Ali M, S. K. M and S. K, "A Review - Breast Cancer Detection using Deep Learning Methods," *2022 6th International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology*, Coimbatore, India, 2022, pp. 569-574, doi: 10.1109/ICECA55336.2022.10009307.
- [7] S. N. Eldin, J. K. Hamdy, G. T. Adnan, M. Hossam, N. Elmasry and A. Mohammed, "Deep Learning Approach for Breast Cancer Diagnosis from Microscopy Biopsy Images," *2021 International Mobile, Intelligent, and Ubiquitous Computing Conference (MIUCC)*, Cairo, Egypt, 2021, pp. 216-222, doi: 10.1109/MIUCC52538.2021.9447653.
- [8] R. B. Mim, A. B. Islam, S. Roy and A. Sattar, "Breast Cancer Detection using Machine Learning Approach," *2022 International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Energy Technologies (ICECET)*, Prague, Czech Republic, 2022, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/ICECET55527.2022.9872893.
- [9] S. Sharma, A. Aggarwal and T. Choudhury, "Breast Cancer Detection Using Machine Learning Algorithms," *2018 International Conference on Computational Techniques, Electronics and Mechanical Systems (CTEMS)*, Belgaum, India, 2018, pp. 114-118, doi: 10.1109/CTEMS.2018.81.